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DEPT. OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Investigation of Similarities and Dissimilarities of Skin Lesions (Melanoma/Non-Melanoma) Using Convolutional Neural Network

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Topic of the Thesis:

(Upon consulting with your supervisor, give a 150-300-word-long synopsis of your planned thesis.)

Motivation:

Nevus and melanoma are a group of neoplasia. Although nevi (plural of nevus) and melanomas are often treated as independent entities, there is evidence that a nevus can be a precursor for a melanoma. Melanoma is a type of skin cancer that develops when melanocytes (the cells that give the skin its tan or brown color) start to grow out of control. So, our major goal is to build up a classifier to distinguish between Melanoma and Non-melanoma cases (our interest is to distinguish all other categories of skin problems from the most dangerous category, i.e., from melanoma).

In particular, the goal is to reduce the classifier's false-negative rate (cases when the classifier labels it as non-melanoma, but the images are representing melanomas) to improve the classifier's overall performance.

Dataset:

ISIC 2019 (<https://challenge2019.isic-archive.com/>) and ISIC 2020 (<https://challenge2020.isic-archive.com/>) – Both are publicly available Skin Lesion Data Sets.

Task List:-

- DenseNet169 (<https://www.kaggle.com/pytorch/densenet169>) and other deep networks for pre-processing.
- Set up similarities and dissimilarities (pair) using [1], details:
 - Embedding into low dimensional space (for clustering and visualization)
 - human knowledge-based pairings based on common sense and experts' opinion
 - machine clustering using graph cut in 2D and 3D
- Use a TensorBoard-based (<https://www.tensorflow.org/tensorboard>) online, interactive interface (NIPGBoard) to project the results of the deep representation of the deep mesh into 3D space.
- Constrained pairwise loss for improvements
 - Considering methods to improve pairwise losses, e.g., triplet losses
- Evaluate the dataset:
 - Apply graph cutting methods such as Girvan-Newman community detection algorithm, Louvain community detection algorithm, Spectral clustering, Agglomerative Clustering, etc. to automate the search for clusters and look for false-negative clusters that are of good quality (for clarification: good quality means that the items considered to be in the same cluster are mostly having the same information or label).
 - Extract the corresponding teacher and test data from the data set and improve the bad clusters.

References:

[1] Hsu, Y. C., & Kira, Z. (2015). Neural network-based clustering using pairwise constraints. arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.06321.

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Abstract

Skin cancer is commonly occurring and one of the deadliest cancer among patients. Dealing with melanoma becomes more challenging because of the fact that malignant cancer and a non-dangerous mole can look alike. The similar size, color, shape, and many other visual attributes make the correct diagnosis more difficult even for human experts. A combination of high-quality dermoscopic images, convolutional neural networks, and human experts' knowledge has been proved a great success in automatic skin cancer diagnostics.

Our goal is to improve the feature extraction performance of ensemble algorithms by filtering out the false negative (FN) and true negative (TN) samples. Also, to investigate them in more detail using the combination of machine learning, feature extraction, and visual inspection. We selected a PyTorch ensemble algorithm as a primary model for feature extraction and carried on the experiment with only FN and TN embeddings. Different dimension reduction algorithms (PCA, t-SNE, UMAP) were applied on the multidimensional embedding. The 3D outputs were later used to find cluster formation using the Louvain community detection algorithm and NIPGBoard online visualization interface. We integrated human knowledge to the Louvain graph cut output and identified three final clusters (named A, B, and C) that have unique characteristics.

Cluster A was a pure TN cluster, needs no further investigation, cluster B was affected by a digital scale pattern (dermatoscopy feature) and cluster C contained the most problematic TN-FN images. Support vector machine (SVM) and Kira pairwise constraints were applied on the three main clusters to investigate them in detail regarding the TN-FN image distribution. The different factors associated with the clusters and the conclusions based on NIPGboard visualization can improve future researches of dermatologists and also facilitate expert cooperation.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Motivation	3
1.2	Goals	4
1.3	Summary of Research Plan	5
1.4	Organization of the Thesis Paper	7
2	Literature Review	9
2.1	Dermoscopic Image Data	9
2.2	Feature Extraction of Images	10
2.2.1	Convolutional Neural Networks	10
2.2.2	Dimensionality Reduction Algorithms	12
2.3	Network Analysis	14
2.3.1	Community Detection	14
2.4	Classification Algorithms	15
2.4.1	Support Vector Machine	15
2.4.2	Random Forest	16
2.4.3	K-nearest Neighbour	17
2.5	Confusion Matrix	18
3	Methodology	20
3.1	Pre-trained Model and Ensemble Technique	20
3.2	Data Preparation	21
3.3	Feature Extraction from Pre-trained Model	23
3.4	Hyper-parameter Tuning	23
3.5	Kira Algorithm	26
3.6	Visualization Tool	27

3.7	Automatic or Hand-based Pairing of Images Using NIPGBoard	28
4	Experiments	31
4.1	Embedding Extraction for TN and FN Images	31
4.2	Feature Embedding Projection and Dimension Reduction	32
4.3	Cluster Formation with Louvain Algorithm	34
4.4	Merging Clusters with Human Intelligence	37
4.5	Test Sample Classification	38
4.6	TN-FN Image Separation inside Clusters A, B, C	40
4.6.1	Further Processing	41
5	Experimental Results	44
5.1	Combining Louvain Clusters	44
5.2	Output of Subset Test Samples classification	48
5.3	Cluster Processing with SVM	49
5.4	Cluster C Processing with Kira Method	51
6	Conclusion & Future Work	54
6.1	Conclusion	54
6.2	Future Work	56
	Bibliography	57
	List of Figures	63
	List of Codes	65

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Skin lesions can be of different types such as moles that are very common and benign (non-cancerous). Although, probability of common moles turning into cancer is very rare and most people having moles anywhere on their skin should not be worried. However, still, there are chances that moles might grow out of control on the skin and be a precursor of cancer (melanoma). Early detection of distressed skin lesions can reduce the further treatment costs and the regular, careful medical investigation can decrease the chance of skin cancer with a good percentage [1]. Fundamentally, melanoma and non-melanoma are the most studied skin cancer types [2]. Furthermore, it is quite hard to distinguish melanoma skin lesions from non-melanoma due to their identical visual appearance [3]. Attributes such as size, shape, color, border, irregularity, or abruptness are all providing opportunities for false negative classification of melanoma. Studying this type of cancer - especially with the motivation towards automatised diagnosis - is a current topic nowadays [4], [5], [6], [7]. According to a recently conducted research [8], minimum one in five Americans will develop skin cancer in their lifetime and approximately 9,500 people in the U.S. are diagnosed with different types of skin cancers every day. Also, different countries like the United Kingdom reported around 2,300 melanoma skin cancer deaths every year, that is more than 6 every day (2016-2018) [9]. Manual detection of melanoma needs well-trained specialists (dermatologists) which can be very challenging depending on the experience level of the expert. Therefore, the automatic classification of

skin lesions can drastically lower the dermatologist's workloads, eliminate the repetitive and routine tasks, and improve dermatological care access [10]. Moreover, the COVID-19 situation has escalated the exigency of the remote diagnosis like never before. Teledermoscopy has paved the path for the easier remote diagnosis in one click for skin-related issues such as skin cancer, skin pigmentation etc. [11]. Mobile teledermatology might be used to administer filtering or triage system which will help manage patients with emergent skin diseases in a more reasonable way [11], [12]. With the advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), available dermoscopic image data [13], and teledermoscopy, a significant effort and combination of human knowledge and convolutional neural network (CNN) have been proved a great success in automatic (& remote) skin cancer diagnostics at their initial stage and eradication [14], [4].

1.2 Goals

Inaccurate detection of a malignant skin lesion as benign (false negative condition) is more detrimental than misdiagnosing a benign skin lesion as malignant (false positive condition). The first case can be lethal due to insufficient treatment and cause life-threatening consequences [15]. The higher rate of false negative diagnosis of melanoma is the main challenge for early treatment.

The focus of this research is to improve the performance of feature extraction of ensemble algorithms by filtering out the false negative (FN) and true negative (TN) samples and investigating them in more detail (similarities and dissimilarities) using the combination of machine learning (clustering), neural network feature extraction, and human knowledge (e.g visual inspection) - these are the key techniques used in this experiment. Uncovering the differences between TN and FN images in terms of features (shape, color, contrast) and distance in multidimensional feature space will not only enhance the performance of the classifier, but also will help to reduce the false negative diagnosis subsequently. Throughout the experiment, our focal point was to try separating the TN and FN images from each other, investigate and explain the separation success/failure using a stack of successive steps (mentioned below).

1.3 Summary of Research Plan

The research plan for this project contains the following steps:

- Choosing high-quality, labeled, and online available dataset about skin lesions. Pre-processing the data as creating optimal sized dataset portions with proper distributions for our task. Selection of a pre-trained CNN model (primary) for classifying dermoscopic images into melanoma and non-melanoma classes. Use the CNN to get feature embedding for the true negative (TN) and false negative (FN) images.

- Projection of the FN and TN image's feature embedding into the 3D representation space with the help of dimension reduction methods. The visual inspection can be done in two different ways: using the NIPGBoard interface or using python (matplotlib). NIPGBoard visualization tool is a modified version of Google's Tensorboard [16] and also extended with extra features.

It helps with the initial visual inspection of the primary model output by calculating the Euclidean distance of the involved (FN and TN) images (embedding) in the projection space. Note that, NIPGBoard is an automated visualization tool for non-coders while the same visualization can be done directly by using the programming languages (python). The main difference between them is that we can actually display the images from the dataset on NIPGBoard's projection space (together with the useful functions of the interface such as: zoom in/out, resizing etc.), while using python we can see the images in an abstract way: as 3D points (this lacks the opportunity of investigating the visual features as comparing them to each other).

In the case of the NIPGBoard interface, the following additional subtasks are carried out in order to get the visualization:

- Save the higher dimension projection points into a .text file along with their corresponding labels (FN/TN).
- Upload the projection points onto NIPGBoard.
- Apply different dimension reduction (3D) algorithm (PCA/UMAP/t-SNE).

- Visualize them (how the FN/TN images are clustered together) in the 3D embedding space of NIPGboard.
 - Finalize the better working dimension reduction algorithm (in our case UMAP) by tuning the hyper-parameters.
 - Download the final 3D projection points for further processing.
- After receiving projection points for 3D space, we continue with applying Louvain graph cut algorithm to automatize the cluster searching. Next step is to determine the accuracy index of the found clusters. The accuracy index is calculated by the maximum number of TN/FN images divided by the total number of FN and TN images within the corresponding cluster.
 - Once the clusters are detected and the accuracy index is calculated we define the quality of the clusters. The quality of a cluster is determined by how tightly or loosely FN and TN images are clustered together using an accuracy index (%). If a cluster is having accuracy higher than a given threshold (%) it is considered to be a good quality cluster, on the other hand, if it does not meet the threshold value it is called a mixed cluster. Mixed attribute means the similar number of TN and FN images in the cluster. We drop the high-quality (pure) clusters from further processing and continue the experimental steps with the predefined mixed quality clusters.
 - Enhance the performance of the primary model by applying Kira method [17] to the top layers. Kira is a technique that uses the primary network model as a backbone and pairwise information of the images (similarity or dissimilarity) as input.

The mixed clusters are given as input to the model whose structure was modified with the Kira algorithm. The goal is to locally separate the FN and TN images from each other in the 3D embedding space while using their pairwise constraints.
 - Our goal in the research is to separate the FN and TN images from each other and find the most high-quality clusters. The higher number of such clusters denote the success of the separation of FN and TN images. For the other

clusters, it is also part of the research to try to explain the poorer performance in those cases. This research pipeline leads to a careful investigation and either the creation of high-quality clusters or the explanation of the mixed image groups.

1.4 Organization of the Thesis Paper

The chapters of this thesis are broken down and summarized below:

Chapter 1 (Introduction)

This chapter first shows the motivation behind the conducted research and emphasizes our goal. The content places the topic in the wider interests and justifies its importance. Then it continues with a brief summary of the research plans which will be discussed elaborately in the consecutive chapters. The organization of the thesis paper is also explained in this section.

Chapter 2 (Literature Review)

It represents the literature review conducted on the investigation of similarities and dissimilarities of skin lesions (melanoma/non-melanoma). Starting with the basic information about dermoscopic skin images and the data availability, this section proceeds to explain the different types of feature extraction methods and automatic cluster searching techniques and their architectures.

Chapter 3 (Methodology)

This chapter broadly explains the methods and techniques that have been used to improve the performance of the primary classifier by trying to find out the cluster forming of its output TN-FN images and separating them using traditional machine learning and neural network approaches. It begins with data preparation for the experiment, then followed by information about the used pre-trained model to extract feature embedding, application of cluster searching algorithms, and parameter tuning. At the end of this chapter, the application of the Kira algorithm is shown together with details about the NIPGBoard visualization tool. The section

also emphasizes the integration of the Kira method into the NIPGBoard interface and the automatically generated pairwise constraints of the images are discussed.

Chapter 4 (Experiments)

This section discusses the investigations that were conducted during the thesis work: steps taken to improve the performance of the primary classifier and find clusters. It also explains how and why human intervention is important and also necessary in order to finalize the clusters for further process. The chapter ends with an explanation of the advantages and disadvantages of the support vector machine (SVM) and Kira method. Further evaluation steps with the defined clusters are also included. The aim of this chapter is to explain the experiment in general, and only show the most relevant information in each step. The more detailed evaluation can be seen in the final chapter.

Chapter 5 (Experimental Results)

This chapter shows visual and numerical information of the research work's mid-term and final results as figures, charts, and tables. The main outcome is shown in detail, together with the necessary substeps. This section explains how clusters A, B, C were achieved from Louvain algorithm output, further proceeding with SVM and Kira methods. Numerical details as cluster accuracy and test sample classification results are also shown in detail.

Chapter 6 (Conclusion & Future Work)

This is the last chapter of our research study, which summarizes and concludes the research. This chapter explains the final achievement from the whole work together with the current technical and methodological limitations. It emphasizes the useful metadata-like information that we could gather from the actual data and finally ends with the indication of a future opportunity for this experiment.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

2.1 Dermoscopic Image Data

A dermatoscope is a well-known handheld device in the field of dermatology that uses visible light such as LED bulbs to examine the dubious skin surface [18]. Dermatoscope has become a very important tool to aid diagnosis by specialist clinicians such as dermatologists. Dermoscopy enhances the sensitivity and specificity for the recognition of skin cancers compared with inspection by the bare eye which helps to detect thinner and smaller cancer cells. ISIC 2019 image dataset [19] is a collection of 25,331 such dermoscopic skin lesion images from nine different categories of cancer which were used in the ISIC challenge [6] in 2019 for Skin Lesion Analysis Towards Melanoma Detection. Example images of the dataset are shown in Figure 2.1. The nine different diagnostic categories of skin lesions are namely melanoma, melanocytic nevus, basal cell carcinoma, actinic keratosis, benign keratosis, dermatofibroma, vascular lesion, squamous cell carcinoma and none of the others [20]. During the experiment, as classification categories, we have considered only two classes, one **melanoma** and any other skin lesion which is not melanoma was denoted as **non-melanoma** (such as basal cell carcinoma, actinic keratosis, benign keratosis, etc.)

Figure 2.1: Different types of skin lesions example images from ISIC2019 [6]

2.2 Feature Extraction of Images

In machine learning, feature extraction is the process of identifying and extracting attributes (or so called features) from a large amount of data such as images or text. Feature extraction aims to reduce the redundant feature from the data set using some functional mapping. It helps to build the model with less machine effort and fewer features will be required to capture the same information which intensifies time and cost-effectiveness.

2.2.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

A convolutional neural network (CNN) is a type of neural network that is particularly designed to process pixel-like data (like simple images) [21]. A CNN model is a combination of two components: feature extraction and classification (simplified illustration can be seen on Figure 2.2). The convolution and pooling layers combinedly perform feature extraction from images. The convolution layer is the main building block of CNN architecture and feature extraction process. Convolution is a mathematical operation on two functions [22].

Convolution is applied to the input image using a convolution kernel which produces a feature map. Spatially these kernels are smaller than the input image and consist of weights. The convolution layers absorb complex features (feature maps) by building next to each other. After each convolution operation (kernel), a non-linear activation function [23] is applied to introduce non-linearity to the model. The initial convolutional layers identify the edges, which are then combined with the next layers which detect shapes, the consecutive layers merge this information to detect more prominent features from the image. The convolutional layers can be followed by either a convolutional or a pooling layer. Pooling layers perform dimension reduction on the feature map from the previous layer.

Similar to the convolutional layer, the pooling layer also operates with the help of kernels but without weights. Pooling layers aggregate information within each small region of the feature map. There can be two main types of pooling - max pooling and average pooling. The goal of this layer is to reduce the number of parameters, improve efficiency, and limit the chance of overfitting. The feature extraction is followed by the classification block, which consists of one or a few numbers of fully connected layers [24]. The outputs of convolution and pooling layers are 3D vectors while the fully connected layer in the classification block expects a 1D vector as input. This is why it is important to flatten the output of the final pooling layer.

Figure 2.2: CNN feature extraction architecture [25]

2.2.2 Dimensionality Reduction Algorithms

Dimensionality reduction is an efficient technique of transforming huge data attributes to lower dimensions by preserving the most relevant information or without losing more information [26]. A few advantages of the dimensionality reduction technique are removing multi-collinearity of the parameters which improves model performance and it also helps to visualize data in low dimensional space like 3D or 2D [27].

PCA

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a process of calculating the principal components which are basically eigenvectors. These principal components are used to perform a change of basis on the data by keeping the most important components and leaving the rest of them. Principal components (PCs) are a set of new orthogonal variables and they display the pattern of similarity of the observations. The variation of PCs decreases as we move from the 1st PC to the last one, consequently the importance [28].

The performance of the PCA model can be assessed using cross-validation techniques such as the bootstrap and the jackknife [29]. PCA is an adjustable tool for the analysis of data sets that may contain multicollinearity, missing values, categorical data, etc. The dataset must be scaled before applying the PCA technique. The results are sensitive to the scaling. The method of PCA follows the steps as, standardizing the whole dataset and calculating the covariance matrix, then calculating the eigenvalues and eigenvectors. Decide the required number of principal components and finally transform the original matrix [30].

T-SNE

T-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) is a dimensionality reduction algorithm to visualize high-dimensional data. It is non-linear. In simple words, t-SNE gives an intuition or understanding of how the data is being presented in a high-dimensional area. It was introduced in the year 2008 by van der Maaten [31]. T-SNE preserves only small pairwise distances or local similarities to maximize variance. The main objective of t-SNE is to project multi-dimensional data to

2- or 3-dimensional space. That means if two points are close in the initial high-dimensional space, they stay close in the resulting low projection space respectively. It works in a way that it calculates the probability of similarity of pairs in high-dimensional space and also calculates the probability of similarity of pairs in the corresponding low-dimensional space [32]. T-SNE will maximize the distance in low dimensional space between points that are most different in high dimensional space. Because of this, the points which are close to one another may form clusters. It is an optimization problem that uses the stochastic gradient descent function to solve it [33]. Another important feature of t-SNE is perplexity which gives an idea of how to balance deliberation between local and global aspects of the data i.e number of closet neighbors of every point.

UMAP

Uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) is a new and one among the foremost popular dimension reduction techniques that were introduced by Leland McInnes in 2018 [34]. It is formed on the concept of manifold learning and ideas from topological data analysis. Most significantly it offers a couple of advantages over t-SNE like speed and better maintenance of the global structure.

UMAP follows quite the same mechanism as t-SNE i.e it builds a high dimensional graph that is the representation of the data then optimizes it to a low-dimensional graph to preserve the structural similarity as much as possible. The initial high dimensional graph is constructed by "fuzzy simplicial complex" [35]. This is a representation of a weighted graph, with edge weights representing the likelihood of two connected points. Once the fuzzy simplicial complex is constructed, UMAP projects the data into lower dimensional space essentially by a force-directed graph layout algorithm. The most common parameters in UMAP are "n-neighbors" and "min-dist". The "N-neighbors" parameter is needed to estimate the number of nearest neighbors to build the initial high-dimensional graph. It effectively controls the balance between global and native structures. "Min-dist" controls how tightly UMAP assembles points in low-dimensional space [36].

2.3 Network Analysis

A network is a representation of structural groups of objects and therefore the relationship between them. Network analysis can be seen as a group of specialized analytical methods that are aiming to analyze and optimize an interconnected network and related elements that have some reference to each other. It can estimate very complex patterns of relationships and incomprehensible amounts of connection are often analyzed to reveal core features of the network [37].

2.3.1 Community Detection

Community detection algorithms are techniques of evaluating how groups of nodes are clustered together or partitioned from one another, it's specially designed for network analysis which depends on one attribute type referred to as edges. A network is a community structure if the nodes of the internal network are densely clumped together into sets, and nodes within the other communities are weakly connected inside an equivalent graph.

There are two main categories of community detection namely agglomerative methods and divisive methods [38]. In agglomerative methods initially, the graph consists of only nodes without edges. The edges are added later on one by one starting from stronger to weaker according to weights. In the case of the divisive method, it follows exactly the opposite mechanism of the agglomerative method. At the beginning the graph is complete. Then at every repetitive step, one edge is taken off, the weight is recalculated. Once a certain number of steps have been performed, we receive clusters of densely connected nodes [39].

Louvain Community Detection

Louvain community detection algorithm is one of the fast community unfolding methods for big network structures. It was created by Vincent Blondel from the University of Louvain [40]. This community detection technique follows the approach of greedy optimization. The inspiration for this method is the optimization of modularity by trying to maximize the distance between the actual number of edges and expected number of edges in a community .

Modularity optimization in a network is an NP-hard problem [41]. This method is based on two iterative phases. In the first phase, each node of the network will be allocated to different communities. Then it will calculate the modularity of each node by removing the particular node from the present community and moving it to the neighbor's community. The node will be only placed into the neighbor's community if the modularity gain is positively maximized otherwise the node will remain in the same community.

This iterative process of the first phase stops when a local maximum of modularity is found. In the second phase, a new network is built by the communities obtained in the first phase as nodes. Once the network is complete from the second phase, the first phase steps will be applied to the network. These steps will be repeated until the maximum modularity is obtained [42].

2.4 Classification Algorithms

In machine learning, classification is a technique to solve problems where input data needs to be categorized into a given number of predefined classes. The aim of the classification technique is to identify the categories of new data among the given number of predefined classes [43]. It is applicable to both structured and unstructured datasets. Classification is a supervised machine learning problem.

The algorithm that is used to map the input data to a specific predefined category is known as a classifier. There are mainly four types of classifications, binary classification, multi-class classification, multi-label classification, and imbalanced classification [44].

2.4.1 Support Vector Machine

Support vector machine (SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm. It is designed for both classification and regression problems [45]. Support vector machine that is used for classification problems and regression problems are known as SVC (support vector classifier) and SVR (support vector regressor) respectively.

The idea behind SVM is to find the optimized line or hyperplane which separates the data into classes. In more detail, we plot all data with n number of features in the

multi-dimensional space where the value of each feature is the value of a particular coordinate. Then, the classification is being performed by trying to find the best fit hyper-plane that separates the two classes in the best way possible with the help of support vectors. Support vectors are data points located near the margin of the hyper-plane that influence the orientation of the hyperplane.

SVC is first outlined for the linearly separable problems [46]. In case the data is not linearly separable then SVM kernel methods are used. Some of the most used kernels in SVM are polynomial, quadratic, and radial basis functions. Their simple visual explanation of the most commonly used kernels can be seen in Figure 2.3. Kernel functions play a very important role in SVM to bridge from linearity to non-linearity by projecting the dataset into a higher dimension in which the data can be linearly separable [47].

Figure 2.3: Three different types of SVM kernels [48]

2.4.2 Random Forest

Random forest [49] is an ensemble learning technique (combining multiple models) for classification and regression to solve large-scale complex problems. This algorithm was proposed L. Breiman in 2001. This approach combines several randomized decision trees and aggregates their predictions by averaging [50], the corresponding illustration in Figure 2.4. The "forest", which is an ensemble of multiple decision trees in the random forest algorithm is trained through bagging or bootstrap aggregation technique. Bagging or bootstrap aggregation are two types of ensemble methods. In case of bagging aggregation, it generates a separate training subset from

sample training data and the final output is decided on majority voting. Random forest is an example of the Bagging technique. While boosting combines weak learners into strong learners by creating sequential models. For classifications, the output of the random forest is the class voted by the maximum number of trees. Whereas for regression, the average prediction of the individual trees [51], [52]. A random forest overcomes the limitations of a decision tree algorithm that is, it reduces the chance of overfitting of datasets and increases precision.

Figure 2.4: Random Forest [53]

2.4.3 K-nearest Neighbour

The k-nearest neighbor's algorithm (k-NN) is a classification technique, initially developed by Evelyn Fix and Joseph Hodges in 1951 [54], later it was extended by Thomas Cover [55].

It is a non-parametric method. K-NN can be used for both regression and classification, but it is broadly used for classification problems.

K in K-NN algorithm is the number of nearest neighbors of the data points to be considered. This value is a positive integer, typically it should be small. The goal of

nearest neighbor methods is to find a predefined number of training samples that are closest to the new data point in terms of distance (metric) and predict the label for the new data point. Those data points that have minimum distance in feature space from the new data points are considered as nearest neighbors. The classifier assigns the category to the new data points depending on the highest number of votes of the closest training samples. The distance between the data points can be calculated by Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, Hamming distance, and Minkowski distance [56].

Figure 2.5: K-NN [57]

2.5 Confusion Matrix

Confusion matrix is an evaluation technique for classification problems [58]. It is an $N \times N$ matrix, where N is the number of target classes. It summarizes the prediction results in terms of correct and incorrect prediction counts which are broken down by each class. The matrix compares the target values with the predicted values by the model. The columns of the confusion matrix represent the actual(true) values of the target variable while the rows represent the predicted values of the target variable.

There are four main values of the matrix: 1) true positive (TP), 2) true negative (TN), 3) false positive and 4) false negative. If the predicted value by the model is positive and the true value is also positive then it is TP, if the true and predicted values both are negative then it is TN. On the other hand, if the predicted value

is negative while the true value is positive it is an FP problem and a type 1 error. Going further, it is a type 2 error if the predicted value is positive, but the true value is negative. With the help of TN, TP, FP, and FN we can calculate the precision, recall and F1-score for the better, more detailed evaluation of the model [59].

Confusion Matrix

	Actually Positive (1)	Actually Negative (0)
Predicted Positive (1)	True Positives (TPs)	False Positives (FPs)
Predicted Negative (0)	False Negatives (FNs)	True Negatives (TNs)

Figure 2.6: Confusion Matrix

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Pre-trained Model and Ensemble Technique

By the simplest definition, a pre-trained model is a deep learning model trained over a large dataset by members of the computer science community or individuals. This network (weight matrix) is then saved, documented, and shared via official repositories to provide free-to-use solutions for similar types of problems in the future. Commonly used models are for example EfficientNet [60], VGG16 [61], DenseNet121 [62] etc. These pre-trained models are freely available online [63]. These are image classification models which are trained on ImageNet [64] data. ImageNet is a large collection of image data consisting of 1000 categories of images. These pre-trained models are capable of classifying any set of (new) images outside of the ImageNet dataset that falls into the given 1000 categories that the dataset contains. The advantages of such a pre-trained model are: it requires minimal setup due to the previously learned weights, hence time and cost-effective and there is no need to build a network from scratch.

The ensemble method is a combination of a diverse set of models instead of using a single model to obtain better accuracy and predictive power. This is also known as committee-based learning as it combines multiple learners to solve a problem [65]. The model that has been used to extract the feature embedding in this experiment is an improved state-of-the-art of Kaggle award-winning method of the 2020 SIIM-ISIC skin lesion classification challenge [7]. It is an ensemble convolution neural network (CNN) model with different backbones such as the EfficientNet family

ranging from b3 to b7, a ResNet model and a Squeeze-and-Excitation-ResNeXt model [66]. A small number of convolutional neural networks were added to provide interpretability. This ensemble model was developed using the Pytorch framework. The averaging method of the 2020 SIIM-ISIC skin lesion classification challenge was replaced by a committee machine, a shallow neural network. Out of many different architectures for the committee machine, the optimally used layers are three fully connected hidden layers consisting of 128, 64, and 32 neurons, with a dropout of 0.5 after each layer. This ensemble model namely Ensemble EfficientNet model was trained on combination of the classification dataset of ISIC2018 [5], ISIC2019 [6] and ISIC2020 [7].

3.2 Data Preparation

The starting dataset for the experiment is ISIC2019 [6], we filtered and relabelled it for our purposes. We have the true labels (0 as non-melanoma and 1 as melanoma) and softmax prediction values from the ensemble model of all $\sim 25\text{K}$ ISIC2019 data. As in the experiment, the goal is to reduce the false negative rate of the classifiers, we are only interested in false negative (FN) and true negative (TN) images. The 55 % threshold was decided using the roc curve [67] to convert the probability predictions (softmax) to a binary number (0/1).

Final data preparation steps:

- Take the ISIC2019 database, compare the true labels and binary prediction to obtain the TN and FN images. If the prediction is 0 and the ground truth is also 0, then it is a TN image, if the prediction is equal to 0 and the ground truth is 1, then it is an FN image.
- Now we have a $\sim 21\text{K}$ sized, filtered "TN-FN dataset" from ISIC2019.
- Shuffle the "TN-FN dataset" to add randomness.
- We have a $\sim 21\text{K}$ sized "TN-FN dataset". This dataset is TN-dominated and ~ 846 are FN images and $\sim 20\text{k}$ are TN images.

- Divide the "TN-FN dataset" into train and test set while following the rule: divide both the FN images and TN images into 75% train and 25% test ratio. The outcomes are the Train dataset and the Test dataset.
- The final experiment was carried out with the smaller subsets of the Train dataset and Test dataset, namely Subset Train and Subset Test. This was a necessary change in the sample numbers due to NIPGBoard capacity and visualization feasibility.

Please refer to figure 3.1 for the overview of data preparation. As mentioned earlier the TN-FN dataset was shuffled randomly at the beginning, hence the output we will receive on Subset Train and Subset Test will be also true for the Train dataset and Test dataset correspondingly.

Figure 3.1: Data preparation

3.3 Feature Extraction from Pre-trained Model

Among all CNN backbone models of ensemble model, the Efficient-net B2 [60] was chosen to extract the embedding of FN-TN images due to its more convincing output. As the model was already trained on ISIC2019 [6], so we do not re-train the model on FN and TN images. We use the model to obtain the embedding of the FN-TN images which will be further used to project on the visualization tool after dimension reduction. Each layer of any CNN model outputs an embedding vector, so the decision needs to be taken which layer's output (embedding) to use for further processing. The final embedding used is a convolutional 2D layer. It is a 1792D embedding vector. More details about the final layers of the Efficient-net B2 model are shown in Figure 3.2.

```
(conv_head): Conv2d(448, 1792, kernel_size=(1, 1), stride=(1, 1), bias=False)
(bn2): BatchNorm2d(1792, eps=0.001, momentum=0.1, affine=True, track_running_stats=True)
(act2): SwishMe()
(global_pool): AdaptiveAvgPool2d(output_size=1)
(classifier): Identity()
)
(dropouts): ModuleList(
  (0): Dropout(p=0.5, inplace=False)
  (1): Dropout(p=0.5, inplace=False)
  (2): Dropout(p=0.5, inplace=False)
  (3): Dropout(p=0.5, inplace=False)
  (4): Dropout(p=0.5, inplace=False)
)
(mvfc): Linear(in features=1792, out features=9, bias=True)
```

Figure 3.2: Final layers of Efficient-net B2 model

3.4 Hyper-parameter Tuning

Hyper-parameters are the arguments or adjustable parameters of a model we choose to govern the model learning process. There is no predetermined way for finding out the method in which hyper-parameters can be tuned to reduce the loss. It can be considered as a trial and error experimentation. This is a key technique in machine learning to obtain the desired output. Hyper-parameters are tuned to get the best fit model. Tuning is a process of optimizing the model's performance to avoid overfitting/underfitting or creating too high of a variance. Hyper-parameters differ for the different datasets. Generally, searching for the best hyper-parameter

follows the two steps: 1) for each proposed hyper-parameter train the model and evaluate the accuracy 2) keep repeating the first step until the best model is found. These steps can be automatized using a few other methods such as GridsearchCV.

GridsearchCV

One way of hyper-parameter tuning is a manual trial and error process. This can be cumbersome and time-consuming and it can take a lot of time just to build a single model. GridsearchCV is a method of looping through the predefined hyper-parameters and fitting the model on the training set. At the end of this process, it offers the best parameters among all the predefined ones. In GridsearchCV, grid search and cross-validation are also performed in parallel. GridsearchCV is available as a function in SK-Learn `model_selection` package (Figure 3.3).

estimator is the selected model.

param_grid is a predefined dictionary with parameter names as keys and parameters as values.

cv is an integer number indicating the folds cross-validation.

scoring is performance evaluation metric.

A code snippet showing the initialization of a GridSearchCv object. The code is: `1 clf = GridSearchCv(estimator, param_grid, cv, scoring)`. The code is displayed in a light gray box with a dark gray border and a play button icon on the left side.

Figure 3.3: GridsearchCV

UMAP Parameters

UMAP has four basic parameters: n-neighbors, min-dist, n-components, and metric. In the experiment, as the focus is on 2D/3D projection of the embedding, n-component is set to 2 or 3 correspondingly for 2D and 3D UMAP, min-dist and metric are set to default [68]. After many iterations of parameter tuning the best value for n-neighbour is set to 43. An illustration of the setup can be seen in Figure 3.4.

```

1 def draw_umap(n_neighbors=43, min_dist=0.1, n_components=3, metric='euclidean'):
2     fit = umap.UMAP(
3         n_neighbors=n_neighbors,
4         min_dist=min_dist,
5         n_components=n_components,
6         metric=metric
7     )

```

Figure 3.4: UMAP Class

SVM Parameters

There are a few numbers of parameters in the SVM model, but the two most important ones are kernel and C. Kernel can have 5 types: 'linear', 'poly', 'rbf', 'sigmoid', 'precomputed'. C is a regularization parameter. This parameter indicates the optimization process to how much to avoid misclassification of the training model. It is a trade-off between smooth decision boundaries and the classification of the training points. The final value for C was 10 and the chosen kernel was 'rbf'. The rest of the parameters were left default. The overview of the chosen parameters is displayed in Figure 3.5.

```

1 class sklearn.svm.SVC(C=10, kernel='rbf',
2                       degree=3,
3                       gamma='scale',
4                       coef0=0.0, shrinking=True, probability=False,
5                       tol=0.001, cache_size=200, class_weight=None,
6                       verbose=False, max_iter=-1, decision_function_shape='ovr',
7                       break_ties=False, random_state=None)

```

Figure 3.5: SKlearn SVM Class

Louvain Parameters

The two most important parameters in the Louvain community detection algorithm are the resolution parameter and distance metric (Figure 3.6). The distance metric finds the specified number of nearest neighbors. While the resolution parameter determines the size of the found clusters. If the resolution is smaller, then the size recovered cluster is small, therefore, conversely, it recovers a bigger cluster with more data points if the resolution is large.

Let's consider there is a network f , we feed data x_p and x_q into that network and get two distributions P and Q . If P and Q come from a similar pair, then we define the cost as plain KL-divergence; otherwise, it is the hinge loss (still using divergence). This approach supports both full pairwise and partial pairwise constraints for supervised training or semi-supervised respectively. The significant advantage of the method is when the number of clusters is unknown. The workflow diagrams and illustrative comparison are shown in Figure 3.7 [17].

Figure 3.7: Comparison of different networks [17]

3.6 Visualization Tool

The NIPGBoard is a data visualization tool developed by the Neural Information Processing Group (NIPG) at Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Informatics. The implementation is based on TensorBoard [16], which is made for inspecting experiments done with the Tensorflow package and it is developed by Google. The TensorBoard plugins are integrated into the NIPGBoard system. This interface is developed to simplify the human-machine interaction.

The key idea is the interactive visualization interface, an example screenshot can be seen in Figure 3.8.

Another aim of the NIPGBoard is to represent the data in human-interpretable

form by projecting them in a low dimensional (2D/3D) space. Since artificial neural networks work on high-dimensional data and it is beyond human understanding to comfortably analyze such information. The main area of the NipgBoard interface is called projection space and it displays the chosen dimension reduction method's (PCA, UMAP, or t-SNE) output. The data points are represented as "sprite images": the miniature versions of the real data. The opportunity of investigating the whole data visually, together with the similarity/dissimilarity relations is a great help for human experts to gain better knowledge about the true nature of the data. The corresponding metadata can be displayed as well for each image: usually, the label is the most informative data to be shown.

A few of the features of NIPGBoard are: it is accessible from a web server, starting the project on the local machine via web browser, optional dimension reduction algorithms, parameter tuning options of the algorithms, running and retraining of different deep neural network algorithms such as DenseNet[62] (default). Additionally, the Kira algorithm is also integrated into NIPGBoard. As Kira follows pairwise constraint (for more details please check section 3.7), it gives an opportunity to retrain the output of the default deep learning network (which is also integrated to NIPGBoard) with similarity and dissimilarity relations between data points.

Then we can compare the output of the default deep neural network and the newly created Kira-supported model. With the visualization of the dimension reduction method, we can also investigate if there is any improvement (in terms of classification) on the data.

3.7 Automatic or Hand-based Pairing of Images Using NIPGBoard

Kira algorithm is also integrated into NIPGBoard. To run the Kira algorithm the pairwise information needs to be provided for the data points. Pairwise information can be the visual similarity or dissimilarity of two images. According to the function names in the interface if the two images are similar, then it is called a positive pairing, otherwise, it is a negative pairing. Positive pairing is denoted by green connection

Figure 3.8: NIPGBoard visualization interface with an example of Kira pairing

lines and for negative pairing, it is denoted by red.

The interface only visualizes the connections that are created by the user, and these are called direct relations. The indirect relations are visually invisible, but existing pairs in the interface, and defined by the pairing action's transient attribute. This means if A and B images are connected with similarity relation, and B and C images are also in positive relations, then transient means that A and C are also indirectly connected with similarity relation.

Figure 3.9: Simplified explanation of positive and negative Kira pairing

Figure 3.9 is a simplified illustration of the positive and negative pairing process. However, NIPGBoard provides two options for pairing the images: 1) automatic pairing, 2) hand-based pairing. In the case of automatic pairing, the number of data

points to be paired can be given with percentages. In this case, random images will be selected for negative and positive pairing according to the given percentage.

As the other method: hand-based pairing is considered as the careful selection of images to be paired together after visual inspection by the user. It is slower to accomplish, but this is the opportunity of the human special (domain) knowledge to enhance the data understanding. In addition to the directly given connections, the Kira algorithm will process the transient ones as well during the training procedure.

Chapter 4

Experiments

In this chapter, we will cover every procedure in detail which was mentioned briefly in the 1.3 subsection of the first chapter. We will go through every detail starting from the first processing step when the embedding was extracted and projected in the NIPGBoard interface. After that section, we are continuing with the explanation of how the number of clusters was decided and further evaluated in different ways that could be Kira or SVM methods.

4.1 Embedding Extraction for TN and FN Images

We choose one of the best performing models (EfficientNet B2) from Ensemble EfficientNet for the feature extraction of FN-TN images. We input both Subset Train and Subset Test to the model in order to get the deep representation (embedding) of the network output which is a 1792 dimensional vector. The next step was to normalize the data (vector). Normalization ensures that the pixel values have a similar data distribution. This leads to faster convergence during the training process. Moreover, dimension reduction algorithms such as PCA, t-SNE work better with normalized data.

4.2 Feature Embedding Projection and Dimension Reduction

After the extraction of feature embedding is done, the dimensionality (1792D) of the data needs to be reduced to avoid overfitting, redundancy, and cost optimization. Moreover, as it was mentioned in the earlier sections, human understanding is limited to a few dimensions, so high-dimensional interpretations are not proper for bare eye investigation. This reduction can be achieved by NIPGBoard (interface specialized for non-coders) and Python programming. Code 4.1 shows more details about the related Python code of applying the UMAP method on the data.

In the case of NIPGBoard, we upload the normalized data into NIPGBoard, by default the PCA dimension reduction algorithm is applied to the data. However, there are two more dimension reduction buttons available with the facility of parameter tuning. Three of these dimension reduction algorithms have been investigated.

We found that UMAP worked better as compared to PCA, and t-SNE. UMAP preserves the global structure in the lower dimensions which helped the future separation of TN-FN images better. The better separation of heterogeneous class images leads to the formation of some good quality clusters and faster computation.

We move forward with 3D UMAP projection points for future analysis. NIPGBoard user interface can even help the coders to decide which dimension reduction algorithm to choose and which is the best working parameter while developing the code thus saving a lot of time.

```
1
2 #umap parameter with labels
3 n_neighbors=50
4 n_components=3
5 metric='euclidean'
6 output_metric='euclidean'
7 n_epochs=600
8 learning_rate=0.1
9 init='spectral'
10 min_dist=0.2
11 spread=1.
12 low_memory=True
```

```
13 local_connectivity=1
14 repulsion_strength=2.
15 negative_sample_rate=2
16 transform_queue_size=2.
17 target_metric='categorical'
18 verbose=False
19 unique=False
20 dens_lambda=2.
21 random_state=42
22 dens_var_shift=.01
23 disconnection_distance=np.inf
24 transform_seed=42
25
26
27
28 trans = umap.UMAP(n_neighbors=n_neighbors,
29                   n_components=n_components, metric=metric,
30                   output_metric=output_metric,
31                   learning_rate=learning_rate, n_epochs=n_epochs,
32                   init=init, min_dist=min_dist,
33                   spread=spread, low_memory=low_memory,
34                   local_connectivity=local_connectivity,
35                   repulsion_strength=repulsion_strength,
36                   negative_sample_rate=negative_sample_rate,
37                   transform_queue_size=transform_queue_size,
38                   verbose=verbose, unique=unique,
39                   dens_lambda=dens_lambda, dens_var_shift=
40                   dens_var_shift,
41                   disconnection_distance=disconnection_distance,
42                   random_state=random_state, transform_seed=
43                   transform_seed).fit(X=train_intermediate_output, y=
44                   labels)
45
46 train_embedding_all=trans.transform(train_intermediate_output)
47 test_embedding=trans.transform(test_intermediate_output)
```

Code 4.1: UMAP dimension reduction on Subset Train and Subset Test samples shown as python code

It is important to note that, while transforming the training samples (images

from Subset Train) into UMAP 2D/3D points, the test samples (from Subset Test) should be transformed into the same learned space as training samples. The visualization can be seen in Figure 4.1 for 3D, and in Figure 4.2 for the 2D embedding space. These visual outputs might be slightly different in each run of UMAP because of “random state” parameters. The random state is a parameter for randomness both to speed up approximation steps and solve hard optimization problems. But this randomness will not affect much in finding clusters using graph algorithms in the upcoming steps.

If the range of the 3D feature space’s X, Y, Z axes are different for training and test data, the classification of test samples into the train sample’s representation space is not possible due to the different measures of the center of the spread. This is a step we should remember while classifying test samples in relation to training samples.

Figure 4.1: 3D UMAP visualization of Subset Train samples (red=TN, blue=FN)

4.3 Cluster Formation with Louvain Algorithm

The goal of dimension reduction and 3D projection of data was to find a natural grouping of FN and TN image embedding in the feature space. These visualized

Figure 4.2: 2D UMAP visualization of Subset Train samples (red=TN, blue=FN)

point clouds are also called clusters. Clusters can be also considered as communities, as it refers to the common attributes inside the boundary that are grouped together.

Cluster searching can be automated by various clustering algorithms. In this experiment, we have used the Louvain algorithm. We used the training samples from Subset Train to create a 3D UMAP projection. This was sent forward as input to the Louvain algorithm in order to get clusters for further processing. The resolution parameter of the Louvain algorithm is the most important as it is responsible for changing the size of the communities, it decides the boundaries of the community. Increasing the resolution will increase the boundary or size of the community thus decreasing the cluster number, size, and vice versa.

A careful visual inspection was carried out on the Louvain output, which can be seen in Figure 4.3. The colors are representing different clusters, and the color-coding information can be seen in the upper left corner. Each label contains information regarding the cluster's quality, the majority label, and the number of members that it contains.

According to the accuracy index, the members of the given group, and the calculated

Figure 4.3: Clusters found by the Louvain community detection algorithm

majority label, we defined the following categories for the clusters:

- if the group contains the majority of TN images with an accuracy index greater than 85% then it is a "good_TN" cluster.
- if the group contains the majority of TN images with an accuracy index less than 85% then it is a "mixed_TN" cluster.
- if the group contains the majority of FN images with an accuracy index greater than 85% then it is a "good_FN" cluster.
- if the group contains the majority of FN images with an accuracy index less than 85% then it is a "mixed_FN" cluster.

The outcome of the community detection was 20 clusters, the number of belonging samples was between 27 and 158, the accuracy value was between 56% and 100%. According to the aforementioned rule for naming the clusters based on their accuracy indexes 7 clusters are defined as "good cluster" and 13 as "mixed cluster". Numerical details about the Louvain clusters are described in the 5.1 subsection of the Experimental Result (5th) chapter.

4.4 Merging Clusters with Human Intelligence

This step requires very careful human intervention. This is a phase where human knowledge and AI are combined. Here, the goal is to merge the multiple clusters retrieved from the Louvain algorithm to a fewer number of clusters. With human investigation, it is clear to see (referring to Figure 4.3) that some of these clusters are located close to each other but separated from others. Naturally, some data points fall in the "middle" area, but with a bare eye mainly 3 clusters are to be localized. We aimed to combine the most clusters to achieve the possible smallest number of (bigger sized) clusters, that have a unique character from the matter of TN and FN images.

The motivation behind this is to reduce the number of found small clusters and merge clusters that are close to each other and further treat the big clusters according to their characteristics (e.g. good quality or mixed quality). To achieve this an attentive visual inspection and comparison of NIPGBoard 3D representation, UMAP representation, and Louvain cluster information are needed as a combined effort. The final outcome of the merging process was 3 clusters, namely clusters A, B and C.

Cluster A is a pure TN cluster with 100% accuracy and needs no further treatment. Only 2-3% of the Subset Train fell into this cluster.

Cluster B is a special cluster because of the fact that most of the images inside this cluster are affected by an artificial scale (probably a feature of the dermatoscope recording). More specifically, most of the skin lesion images inside this cluster have a measurement scale on them, which might have a negative effect on the deep neural network training as a prominent feature. This can be also the reason why these images (in their embedding level) are close to each other. So, this cluster needs some expert judgment. However, it still can be considered as a better quality mixed cluster which means the TN percentage is higher with a low amount of FN images. 7-8% of the Subset Train samples belong to this cluster.

Cluster C is in the center of interest due to the fact that most of the population of the Subset Train data belongs here, approx. 90%. This is a highly mixed cluster with approximately the same percentage of TN and FN images. We will try to separate the TN and FN images from this cluster using machine learning approaches and the Kira method. More detailed explanations and descriptions of clusters A, B, and C

are written in the 5.1 subsection of the Experimental Result (5th) chapter.

Figure 4.4: A, B, C clusters represented with green, red and blue respectively.

4.5 Test Sample Classification

After we have the three big clusters, then each test sample (from Subset Test) should be classified into one of the three clusters. We used K-NN ($K=1$, distance=euclidean) to find out for each test sample which is the closest point in the Subset Train data, a sample of code can be seen in Code 4.2. Then the test sample will receive the domain of the cluster where the closest train point belongs to.

More elaborately, let's say there is a test sample P with ground truth as FN. If we want to find out which cluster this point belongs to we have to first find out the closest train sample to it. It can be done using the KNN algorithm where $K=1$. Let's say the closest train sample to P is Q. As in the previous steps we have already classified the train samples among one of the three (A, B, C) clusters, the information that Q belongs to which cluster/domain is already known. So if Q belongs to A/B/C, P will belong to the same cluster correspondingly.

So if Q belongs to a high-quality TN/FN (cluster A) or low-quality TN/FN cluster

(cluster C) then P belongs to the same cluster as well and receives the corresponding label. Code 4.3 shows more details about the progress.

```

1
2 def calculate_k_nearest(train_projections, test_projections,
3     labels_test, distance='euclidean'):
4     nearest_neighbour=[]
5     rows, cols = projections_test.shape[0], projections.shape[0]
6     # matrix_shape = [rows, int(((rows * rows) - rows) / 2)]
7     matrix = np.zeros(shape=(rows, cols))
8     matrix.shape
9     for i in range(rows):
10        min=1000
11        for j in range(cols):
12            if distance == 'euclidean':
13                matrix[i][j] = np.linalg.norm(projections_test[i] -
14                    projections[j])
15                if matrix[i][j]<min:
16                    min=matrix[i][j]
17                    index_train=j
18                    index_test=i
19
20        nearest_neighbour.append([list(projections_test[index_test]),
21            list(projections[index_train]), matrix[index_test][
22                index_train], labels_test[index_test]])
23    return nearest_neighbour

```

Code 4.2: Calculate the K-nearest neighbor

```

1
2 def classify_test_samples(A,B,C,nearest_neighbour):
3     for i in nearest_neighbour:
4
5         if i[1] in A:
6             test_p_A.append(i[0])
7             pred_test_p_A.append(i[3])
8         #-----
9
10        if i[1] in B:
11            test_p_B.append(i[0])

```

```

12     pred_test_p_B.append(i[3])
13     # -----
14     if i[1] in C:
15         test_p_C.append(i[0])
16         pred_test_p_C.append(i[3])
17
18     return test_p_A, pred_test_p_A, test_p_B, pred_test_p_B, test_p_C,
19           pred_test_p_C
20 nearest_neighbour=calculate_k_nearest(projections, projections_test,
21                                     labels_test, distance='euclidean')
22 test_p_A, pred_test_p_A, test_p_B, pred_test_p_B, test_p_C,
    pred_test_p_C=classify_test_samples(A,B,C,nearest_neighbour)

```

Code 4.3: Classification of the test samples using K-nearest neighbor method

4.6 TN-FN Image Separation inside Clusters A, B, C

At this point, we have two options for further analyzing the clusters and studying thoroughly if separation of FN and TN is possible or not. SVM and Kira both have their advantages and disadvantages. Using SVM can not directly make a separation of FN and TN images, or push the FN and TN images away from each other. But, applying SVM can give us a lot of information such as which FN and TN training samples inside the clusters are far from each other (potential formation of high-quality clusters) i.e not near the boundary line (hyperplane) or part of support vectors.

Support vectors are responsible for the better separation of two classes. Miss classification or right classifications are decided by the support vectors. So, if an FN image crosses the boundary (hyperplane) for the TN image or conversely, then those images are the most problematic ones as SVM is unable to classify them correctly. This gives us an idea that these are the FN and TN images which need more investigation on an expert level (as a human specialist) to find out the reason for miss-classification such as color, shape, contrast, size, etc.

While using Kira it gives us an opportunity to separate two opposite class images using pairwise information. This action can be carried out as automatic pairing or as a manual user action via the NipgBoard interface. We can pair two images positively (same class, similarity relation) or negatively (different class, dissimilarity relation) by relying on the displayed labels. Naturally, dermatologists would be able to accomplish this action by only bare eye image inspection.

During this experiment, we have tried both the SVM and Kira methods to analyze the clusters. From both methods we are expecting to be able to visually push away the opposite classes from each other, then we can get high-quality clusters of FN and TN which is our ultimate goal of the research.

4.6.1 Further Processing

This section is about the planning of the cluster evaluation's further steps on each main cluster. The chosen processing option can be the application of SVM, using manual or automatic Kira pairwise constraints or none of these.

Cluster A

Cluster A is a pure TN cluster with a 100% population of TN. After the test sample classification, all the images which were classified inside A were TN. So we do not need to further treat cluster A. We have achieved success with a very high-quality cluster.

Cluster B

Initially, SVM was applied to cluster B to have an overview of the cluster formation, however, we did not apply Kira on Cluster B as the number of images was not enough to train Kira, and also a factor of the scale was there which needs expert level intervention. The test samples which were classified inside this cluster were also affected by the scaling factor which directs our initial theory that the classifier might be misled by the "scaling factor" could be true.

Cluster C

Our work was more cluster C-centric, as it contains 90% of the Subset Train images with most mixed TN & FN images. Moreover, the samples which were classified inside this cluster were of mixed categories of FN and TN images. We applied both Kira and SVM for further investigation. The numerical attributes of the cluster and output of the cluster-specific SVM can be read in the Experimental Results chapter. We applied automatic KIRA pairwise constraints information on the images. All the data points (images) to be connected positively or negatively will be automatically performed by Kira, unlike manual pairing where the NIPGBoard user needs to carefully choose the pairs between data points (images).

In the following paragraph, we are explaining only the main concept and first impressions, the more detailed results are documented in the Experimental Results chapter.

- **Manual Kira Pairing**

Manual pairing depends on the user: how many positive and negative connections he/she wants. For non-specialists, the relevant information available during pairing are the labels of the images (optionally the color overlays) and the image location in the embedding space.

Using Kira pairing in order to improve the 3D UMAP visualization can be done manually with the NIPGBoard interface. Since no extra information is displayed for the images, the only relevant knowledge is about the labels (optionally the color overlays) and the location in the embedding space. This process needs to be focused and iterative work, which is time-consuming, and due to the time constraint for this experiment, we only used automatic pairing. For specialists (domain experts, so in this case dermatologists) naturally, the whole image information is available due to the sprite images, because they have the knowledge about the effective investigation of skin lesion patterns.

Kira can be sensitive to pairing, in detail, pairing any TN-TN, FN-FN positively, or TN-FN negatively from any region might be ineffective in order to separate the images. We landed on this conclusion after many iterations with freely chosen TN-TN, FN-FN, and FN-TN pairs with no improvement in sep-

aration. Showing these efforts in more detail is not connected strongly with the direction of the thesis work, thus it is not included here.

- **Automatic Kira Pairing**

This process requires the percentage to be given by the user, and not the selection of the particular images to be involved in the relations. This ratio(%) means the portion of the corresponding data (for example the X% of the relevant TN samples).

we focused on the concept of automatic pairing instead of using manual pairing due to time constraints. we started automatic pairing of the support vector images. One thing to be noted is that while giving the percentage for the automatic Kira pairing, we should be careful and be aware of the NIPGBoard interface's visualization capacity. If we provide a great percentage, depending on the total image count, it could lead to the memory shortage of NIPGBoard. So, it is a good practice to keep the chosen percentage between 15-25% regardless of the total image count. The final ratios were chosen to be 20% positive and 20% negative pairing on the SV images.

As it is known, support vectors are responsible for defining hyper-planes (in 3D) and thus separating two classes. So, an effort to separate the TN and FN images which are part of support vectors can be proved fruitful in separating all the TN and FN images. If we can make the support vector TN-FN points far from each other, then automatically the non-support vectors will be also more separated from each other. This is the idea for creating an opportunity to find two separate high-quality TN and FN clusters in cluster C.

So, as the decided further processing: we used automatic Kira pairing on the support vector images of cluster C, but only the percentages of the involved TN and FN images were given by us, then the algorithm involved the proper ratios of SV images randomly.

Chapter 5

Experimental Results

This section provides more detailed information about the experiment’s intermediate and final outcomes. Numerical attributes and visualization of the defined clusters can be seen in the structured subsections. The first section introduces the cluster formation after the Louvain community detection algorithm and human knowledge integration. Then this chapter continues with a brief subsection of test sample classification and concludes with a description of cluster processing with SVM and Kira methods.

5.1 Combining Louvain Clusters

Figure 5.1 shows the 3D visual distribution of the Subset Train dataset’s TN (red points) and FN (blue points) labeled images before the final clusters A, B, and C were defined. On the left side, the planning of the merge can be seen, and on the right part the proper colored final clusters. The definition of each cluster is based on the intelligent merging of the Louvain outputs.

We ultimately finalized the total of 20 clusters as Louvain output after parameter tuning, the list of them and the related accuracy index can be seen in Figure 5.2. The name of the clusters depicts the combination of quality and calculation of the majority label. Threshold value to categorize good quality cluster and mixed cluster is 85%.

Later these small clusters were merged together to form clusters A, B and C. To achieve the three main clusters from the UMAP visualization we needed a con-

Figure 5.1: 3D UMAP visualization of cluster A, B, C formation. On the left the TN and FN samples from Subset Train, on the right the manually combined final clusters can be seen

Name of Final Louvain Clusters	Accuracy index [>85%="good" else "mixed"]
good_cluster_TN0	95%
good_cluster_TN1	100%
mixed_cluster_TN3	84%
mixed_cluster_TN4	81%
good_cluster_FN5	91%
good_cluster_FN6	96%
mixed_cluster_FN7	77%
good_cluster_TN8	97%
mixed_cluster_FN9	57%
mixed_cluster_TN10	79%
mixed_cluster_TN11	67%
mixed_cluster_TN12	59%
good_cluster_TN13	91%
mixed_cluster_FN14	56%
mixed_cluster_FN15	67%
good_cluster_TN16	100%
mixed_cluster_TN17	74%
mixed_cluster_FN18	61%
mixed_cluster_TN19	85%

Figure 5.2: List of 20 small clusters from Louvain output on Subset Train data

stant and thorough investigation and visual comparison between the Louvain output (Figure 4.3) and NIPGBoard image visualization (Figure 5.4). This is the part of the research where human intelligence, bare eye visualization, and output of traditional machine learning algorithm were extremely necessary before going towards with the next steps. Figure 5.3 shows the visual distribution of the Subset Train samples in the 3D embedding space after UMAP dimension reduction technique application.

Figure 5.3: Marked regions for the final clusters A, B, C on 3D UMAP. Red points are the TN, blue points are FN samples from Subset Train

In the case of cluster A, it is visually clear that the cluster consists of only red points, that means the belonging points have the same label.

For clusters B and C, the abstract visualization does not provide enough information, so NIPGBoard tool is needed for more careful investigation. One of the advantages of this interface, that it can display miniature versions (called as sprite images) of the real skin lesion images in the representation space. Figure 5.4 is an example screenshot from NIPGBoard visualization. The sprite images have red or blue overlay depending on their label. However, the true nature of the clusters can be revealed even with bare eye investigation: the artificial scale pattern is clearly visible in the images of cluster B.

The third cluster (cluster C) does not show any spectacular visual pattern or label

Figure 5.4: Marked regions for final clusters A, B, C from Subset Train dataset on NIPGBoard interface’s 3D UMAP visualization. Red overlays for TN, blue overlays for FN samples

distribution neither in the Louvain or NIPGBoard outputs, therefore we decided to use SVM for further analysis.

For **Cluster A** the following (2 clusters) Louvain clusters were combined:

- Good cluster TN1 with 100% accuracy
- Good cluster TN16 with 100% accuracy

For **Cluster B** the following (altogether 4 clusters) Louvain clusters were combined:

- Mixed cluster TN4 with 81% accuracy
- Mixed cluster TN17 with 74% accuracy
- Good cluster TN8 with 97% accuracy
- Good cluster13 TN with 91% accuracy

For **Cluster C** the following (14 clusters in total) Louvain clusters were combined:

- good cluster TN0 with 95% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN2 with 62% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN3 with 84% accuracy
- good cluster FN5 with 91% accuracy
- good cluster FN6 with 96% accuracy
- mixed cluster FN7 with 77% accuracy
- mixed cluster FN9 with 57% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN10 with 79% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN11 with 67% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN12 with 59% accuracy
- mixed cluster FN15 with 67% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN17 with 74% accuracy
- mixed cluster FN18 with 61% accuracy
- mixed cluster TN19 with 85% accuracy

5.2 Output of Subset Test Samples classification

We classified the Subset Test samples within clusters A, B, C using K-NN classification algorithm with $K=1$.

Test sample classification results for cluster A:

Total number of 105 TN images and 0 FN images were classified within cluster A, which confirms that cluster A is a pure TN cluster.

Test sample classification results for cluster B:

Total number of 221 TN images and 24 FN images were classified within cluster

B. However, the majority of the TN/FN images which were classified inside this clusters were affected by the "scaling factor".

Test sample classification results for cluster C:

Majority of the subset test images were classified inside the cluster C just same as the training samples, thus making it more prominent that the more detailed investigation is necessary for cluster C. Total number is 863 for TN images and 85 for FN images that were classified within cluster C.

5.3 Cluster Processing with SVM

This section shows the further processing steps and the corresponding outcomes for each defined big clusters (A, B, C) separately.

Cluster A

No further training is needed for cluster A as it is already a 100 percentage TN cluster with 0 number of FN images. The training samples and the test samples are both supporting this outcome.

Cluster B

We trained an SVM algorithm specially on the Subset Train data that belongs to cluster B. GridsearchCV was used for automatically finding best parameters. The optimal setup was the following:

- **Best Parameters:**

- C=10, gamma=0.1

- weights =0:6.5,1:1

- Kernel="rbf"

- Accuracy Metric= "balanced_accuracy_score"

- **Accuracy:**

- Train acc: 0.7845683019567838

- Test acc: 0.6541289592760181

Figure 5.5 is the 3D visualization of SVM output for cluster B. The pink dots refer to TN images and yellow points refer to FN images. Black dots marking are the support vectors points.

Figure 5.5: Cluster B SVM output in 3D representation space

Cluster C

We trained an SVM algorithm specially on the Subset Train data that belongs to cluster C. GridsearchCV was used for automatically finding best parameters. The optimal setup was the following:

- **Best Parameters:**

C=10

gamma=0.1

weights =0:1,1:1

Kernel="rbf"

Accuracy Metric= "balanced_accuracy_score"

- **Accuracy:**

Train acc: 0.775412387177093

Test acc: 0.713441483198146

Figure 5.6 displays the 3D visualization of SVM output for cluster C. The pink dots refer to TN images, yellow points refer to FN images. Black dots marking are the support vectors points.

Figure 5.6: Cluster C SVM output in 3D representation space

5.4 Cluster C Processing with Kira Method

Kira method was applied only on cluster C support vectors as further effort in the TN-FN separation task. This technique requires pairwise constraints provided by the human expert. The final experiment was performed using the automatic pairing function of Kira via NIPGBoard interface.

We considered only support vector images from cluster C for Kira pairing. For our experiment we were given 20% positive and 20% negative pairing request on the cluster C-related support vector images of the Subset Train data, then the Kira algorithm randomly connected the images depending on the percentage calculation. In Figure 5.7 an NIPGBoard screenshot can be seen for support vector images. Sprite images with red overlay are the TN samples, and blue overlaid ones are the FN

data. The overlapping middle area is marked with a black circle.

By using simple codes, we could easily get the information about the support vector image IDs of cluster C from SKLearn "support_" function. It returns indices which are the support vectors. We just needed to filter out those images based on image IDs (indices) and project them on NIPGBoard for Kira application.

Figure 5.8 shows the NIPGBoard's visual output about cluster C support vector

Figure 5.7: Cluster C support vector images in NIPGBoard interface before KIRA pairing. Red overlay is for TN, blue overlay is for FN labels

images after the Kira pairwise constraints were applied. Green lines representing the positive (similarity) connections and red lines are for negative (dissimilarity) relations between images. The used dimension reduction technique was 3D UMAP. For Kira pairwise constraints altogether 829 different similarity relations and 669 dissimilarity relations were established by the automatic kira pairing technique. These are called direct pairs since created directly by the human user.

According to the NIPGBoard's Kira implementation and the transient function, the aforementioned pairwise constraints were extended with 14,940 indirect similarity and 18,499 indirect dissimilarity connections. Indirect pairs are automatically generated by the system.

Comparing Figure 5.7 and Figure 5.8 it is clear with even bare eye investigation that Kira performance on support vectors could not increase the visual separation

Figure 5.8: Cluster C support vector images in NIPGBoard interface after KIRA pairing and training. Red overlay is for TN, blue overlay is for FN labels

of TN and FN images. Due to the same reason we did not separately perform any numerical performance evaluation on Kira output such as accuracy as it would not make difference towards our investigation.

Figure 5.9 shows in the table format the main points, numerical results and the corresponding further processing option for each main clusters.

	Cluster A Accuracy	Cluster B Accuracy	Cluster C Accuracy
SVM output on "Subset Train"	1	0.7845	0.7754
SVM output on "Subset Test"	1	0.6541	0.7134
Further processing	No	No	Yes
Reason	Perfect, non mixed cluster	Special factor appears on images thus domain expert opinion is required	Kira pairwise constraints on support vectors

Figure 5.9: (Table 1) Overview of clusters A, B, C evaluation during the experiments

Chapter 6

Conclusion & Future Work

6.1 Conclusion

We carried out a complex experiment with a focus on the visual separation of TN and FN skin lesion images and an investigation of the possible causes for miss-classifications. The pipeline steps were the followings: we used a pre-trained CNN model for embedding extraction, then filtered out TN-FN images from the output, used dimension reduction techniques, community detection algorithm on the formed clusters, incorporated human intelligence for the proper combination of them, and further processing with SVM and Kira methods. NIPGBoard is an online, interactive visualization interface that played an important role in the evaluation.

As the main outcome we identified three clusters that have unique characteristics, therefore, required different steps for further evaluation.

These clusters are named A, B, and C and the related descriptions and conclusions are the following: Cluster A is a very high quality TN cluster. That means we were successful to separate a portion of the TN-FN dataset from other mixed regions. Hence, in future research work, if any new skin image sample falls visually inside or near this cluster that could be considered as a TN image.

The training accuracy and test accuracy were not satisfactory for Cluster B, thus we cannot state the same conclusion as in the case of Cluster A. However, this detailed investigation unveiled the potential underlying cause of miss-classification in Cluster B: the "artificial scale" factor, which is an easily recognizable pattern in the images. This scale is probably a digital function of the dermatoscope. Since it

can be an important sign for the dermatologist (to compare the skin lesion's size) it cannot be considered as an image recording issue (compare to blurred images), but this significant pattern misleads the deep learning tool and leads towards poor performance. This information now could be investigated by domain experts (dermatologists) and it can be a starting point for more specific expert interaction and collaboration between AI experts and dermatologists.

Training of cluster C performed better than cluster B, the accuracy on the training and test data were higher, still not perfect results. By training cluster C we got the information which is the most problematic images inside the dataset i.e the support vectors. These are the images that are mostly responsible for the miss-classification of the model. Dermatologists now can look inside these images to further analyze them, and it will be a great step towards removing FN classification.

The application of Kira pairwise constraints did not overperform the technique with specially chosen support vectors. Despite it did not lead us to a better clustering, we could at least gather some valuable information about the actual data.

As it was mentioned in the Introduction chapter the complexity and difficulty of distinguishing between simple moles (nevus) and skin cancer (melanoma) is a high-level cognitive task even for human experts. This means, that the visual differences between them can be so slight that they may not have a significant change in the recorded image's visual level, or the difference can be very similar to noise (in terms of machine learning). In real life, dermatologists often recommend minor and short operations, as cutting out the suspicious mole, and then the histology result will give the final diagnosis. It is a safe choice that both the doctor and the patients agree about, but the operation and the histology analysis need time. Deep learning-supported tools are aiming to fasten up and ease the medical experts' workload, so there are still many opportunities for AI to step in.

It is important to continue the search for the reasons of state-of-the-art deep learning tools' false detection. If it is a matter of the recording's quality, then it can help with more detailed image capturing protocols. For example, the appearance of the scale is a visual noise from the point of the model, but it is useful assistance for human experts. So if the cause of miss-classification is more of a hidden phenomenon, then the model should be trained more properly, or as another option: the dataset itself

should be investigated more carefully.

However, Kira's underperformance could be also caused by either the cost function, which was not efficient enough or the stack of neural network layers that need a better architecture. Due to the time constraint, further investigation of Kira's structure was not carried out in more detail. It is also a limitation that the Kira approach is currently restricted by NIPGBoard interface development. As a fast workaround, it can be transferred to jupyter notebooks, but in that case, it will have only basic visualization and very limited interaction possibility.

The NipgBoard's interactive function seems to be essential for efficient information exchange between experts of different scientific fields. The revealed metadata information that is related to the dataset is useful for both dermatologists and computer scientists.

6.2 Future Work

The scope of this experiment in the future is enormous. The ISIC2019 data is biased to white skin, so adding different race skin cancer images will robustify the dataset quality, and enhance the feature classifier's performance. Adding more information received from the SVM and Kira training of the clusters such as the "artificial scale" factor will help to enhance the performance of the model.

The support vector images could be further analyzed by the dermatologists and AI experts using NIPGBoard as a bridge of exchanging information. Kira's structure can be improved with a proper cost function and efficient layers of deep neural networks. Kira's method has the potential to separate unrelated images directly using pairwise information. An efficient Kira structure could remove the need for intermediate steps of investigating similarity and dissimilarity. This same approach can be repeated with a different dataset or combination of ISIC datasets.

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List of Figures

2.1	Different types of skin lesions example images from ISIC2019 [6] . . .	10
2.2	CNN feature extraction architecture [25]	11
2.3	Three different types of SVM kernels [48]	16
2.4	Random Forest [53]	17
2.5	K-NN [57]	18
2.6	Confusion Matrix	19
3.1	Data preparation	22
3.2	Final layers of Efficient-net B2 model	23
3.3	GridsearchCV	24
3.4	UMAP Class	25
3.5	SKlearn SVM Class	25
3.6	Louvain community detection	26
3.7	Comparison of different networks [17]	27
3.8	NIPGBoad visualization interface with an example of Kira pairing . .	29
3.9	Simplified explanation of positive and negative Kira pairing	29
4.1	3D UMAP visualization of Subset Train samples (red=TN, blue=FN)	34
4.2	2D UMAP visualization of Subset Train samples (red=TN, blue=FN)	35
4.3	Clusters found by the Louvain community detection algorithm	36
4.4	A, B, C clusters represented with green, red and blue respectively. . .	38
5.1	3D UMAP visualization of cluster A, B, C formation. On the left the TN and FN samples from Subset Train, on the right the manually combined final clusters can be seen	45
5.2	List of 20 small clusters from Louvain output on Subset Train data .	45
5.3	Marked regions for the final clusters A, B, C on 3D UMAP. Red points are the TN, blue points are FN samples from Subset Train	46

5.4	Marked regions for final clusters A, B, C from Subset Train dataset on NIPGBoard interface's 3D UMAP visualization. Red overlays for TN, blue overlays for FN samples	47
5.5	Cluster B SVM output in 3D representation space	50
5.6	Cluster C SVM output in 3D representation space	51
5.7	Cluster C support vector images in NIPGBoard interface before KIRA pairing. Red overlay is for TN, blue overlay is for FN labels	52
5.8	Cluster C support vector images in NIPGBoard interface after KIRA pairing and training. Red overlay is for TN, blue overlay is for FN labels	53
5.9	(Table 1) Overview of clusters A, B, C evaluation during the experiments	53

List of Codes

4.1	UMAP dimension reduction on Subset Train and Subset Test samples shown as python code	32
4.2	Calculate the K-nearest neighbor	39
4.3	Classification of the test samples using K-nearest neighbor method . .	39

STATEMENT

OF THESIS SUBMISSION AND ORIGINALITY

I hereby confirm the submission of the MSC Thesis Work on the Computer Science for Autonomous course with author and title:

Name of Student: Antika Das

Code of the Student: NU57PS

Title of the Thesis: **Investigation of Similarities and Dissimilarities of Skin Lesions (Melanoma/Non-Melanoma) Using Convolutional Neural Network**

Supervisor: Faragó Kinga Bettina

at Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Informatics.

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